

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN A GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOL (PRIMARY EDUCATION)

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Abstract.

The article discusses the concept of inclusive education and the problems of introducing it to primary school. The rights of children to personal development in a system of education focused on individual needs, including the right of children with developmental disabilities to study in the same schools as their peers living in the neighborhood, are recognized by international human rights standards. Creating conditions for the adaptation of the child to school is to ensure that the child is successful not only in learning but also in the field of communication and interaction between all participants in the educational process: teachers, children, and parents.

Keywords: inclusive education, children with disabilities, integrated learning, WHO, HIA, special education.

The problems of special education today are among the most urgent in education, not only in the Republic of Uzbekistan but throughout the world. This is primarily due to the fact that the number of children with disabilities, according to the WHO, is not steadily growing. In our republic, in recent years, this problem has received great attention from the state and personally from our president.

Sh.M. Mirziyaeva. The "concept of inclusive education until 2030" has been developed. In the new Law on Education, the chapter on "Inclusive Education" is highlighted separately.

Inclusive education is the education of different children in the same class (integrated class). It features the development of the child and his abilities to learn in

an ongoing way that is most suitable for kids. Inclusive education enables all students (including people with disabilities) to complete volume I, participate in the life team, the children's garden, the school, and the institution, and provide additional education to children at the institute. But this does not mean just to collect all the children "in a bunch", Instead, inclusion promotes that every student feel accepted so that his abilities and needs are taken into account and evaluated. Children who need inclusive education may or may not have a disability. Every child is special, that's for sure. And yet there are children who are referred to as "special" not to emphasize the uniqueness of their abilities but to indicate the special needs that distinguish them. There is an urgent need to understand the problems of children with disabilities, to respect and recognize their rights to education, and to be ready to include them in their communities.

Today, children with developmental disabilities do not have to study in specialized institutions; on the contrary, inclusive education allows creating such an educational space for children with disabilities in which any child can be included in the educational and social life of the institution, which will allow him to achieve success and his significance in a peer group. Each child needs to find the degree and form of educational integration that are feasible and useful for him. The introduction of integrated education requires an integrated approach, the creation of a certain environment for the child, the training of specialized teaching staff, and the formation of a tolerant attitude among students and parents toward the problems of "special" children and their problems. We are forced to note that a school without the support and assistance of society cannot create a high-quality model of inclusive education. With the adoption of the new law on education, questions arise about how such children will be taught in our system and how comfortable they will feel at school. How prepared is our school for inclusive education? How do the guys relate to the joint study of equal children? The problem is that children with disabilities are limited by society. A child with disabilities can be just as capable and talented as his peers who do not

have health problems, but to discover their talents, develop them, and bring benefits to society with their help, the opportunity for social adaptation hinders them.

Disabilities of health (HIA). What is it?

The scientific literature describes that children with WHO are characterized by certain limitations in mental, physical, and daily activities. We are talking about physical, mental, sensory, and complex defects. Here I would like to note a number of types of violations.

Violation of mental processes (perception, attention, memory, thinking, speech, emotions, and will)

Violation of the sensory functions (vision, hearing, smell, and touch) is a violation of the musculoskeletal system (ICP).

Violation of the functions of respiration, metabolism, blood circulation, digestion, and internal secretion

WHO Children are distinguished by the presence of physical and mental abnormalities that contribute to the formation of general developmental disorders. Many violations are not limited by the boundaries between the child and the outside world. However, disabled children with serious disabilities need special conditions, special education, upbringing, and treatment.

The basic problem of inclusive education is creating a "barrier-free" educational environment. The main rule is its availability for children with disabilities to solve the problems and difficulties of socialization.

In educational institutions that provide their support, it is necessary to comply with general pedagogical requirements for technical equipment. This is especially true for the implementation of household needs, the formation of competence, and social activity. In addition, special attention should be paid to the upbringing and education of such children.

Despite the ongoing work, it is not so simple when teaching and educating children with disabilities. The existing problems and difficulties of inclusive education are reduced to the following positions:

Firstly, the team of children does not always accept a child with disabilities as "their own."

Secondly, teachers cannot master the ideology of inclusive education, and there are difficulties in implementing teaching methods.

Third, many parents do not want their normally developing children to be in the same class as a "special" child.

Fourthly, not all disabled people are able to adapt to the conditions of ordinary life without requiring additional attention and conditions.

The priority task of modern inclusive education is to increase attention to the socialization of children with disabilities. It is necessary to create and approve adapted programs for children with disabilities to study in a general education school.

On the one hand, as inclusive education in a secondary school begins to manifest itself, the heterogeneity of the composition of students increases, taking into account their speech and mental development. This approach leads to the fact that the adaptation of both conditionally healthy children and children with disabilities is significantly more difficult.

Inclusion everyone child With special needs Educational value and flexibility in learning approaches—these are the main goals of inclusive education.

The main goal of an educational institution is to create special conditions (a universal environment without barriers) for the development and social adaptation of students with special educational needs and their peers.

This security equals right And opportunities for education without discrimination and neglect, the learning process adapts to the needs and educational needs of the child. With the compulsory provision of individual programs for learning,

The system is being adapted to the educational needs of children. Task schools: to prepare a graduate with the necessary set of modern knowledge, skills, and qualities, allowing him to confidently feel himself capable of independent living.

The task of the teacher is to individualize the learning process, bringing it as close as possible to the possibilities of each child. (Required special programs, directed at facilitation of the adaptation process for children with limited opportunities versus a general education institution)

Values of inclusiveness:

- be successful

Belong to society and be part of it.

Lifelong education

for friendship and meaningful relationships

for a full life

Inclusive education on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is regulated by the following documents:

"The Universal Declaration of Human Rights"

"Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities"

"Convention on the Rights of the Child"

UNESCO Education for All Program

Protocol No. 1 of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan The Law on Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan The concept of inclusive education until 2030. Teaching different children in the same class (integrated learning) is based on didactic principles for special and general education.

It should be educational and developmental in nature, which implies the formation of moral representations and concepts, education, adequate ways of behaving, and inclusion all about students' educational activity, contributing to the development of their mental functions and independence.

In integrated learning, it is important to systematically and consistently solve correctional and educational tasks. This includes forecasting and overcoming possible difficulties in the interaction of schoolchildren with different mental abilities.

The principle of an individual and differentiated approach to training should be implemented for students with different educational backgrounds. During the training session on any discipline, it is important to teach everyone but at the same time take into account the abilities of each individual student.

It is equally important that learning be connected to real life. should be modeled and reproduced in situations that are difficult for students but possible in ordinary life; their analysis and playback may become the basis for positive shifts in the development of the student's personality.

The principle of consciousness and activity in the learning process is realized through the use of various tricks for learning, listening to schoolchildren's experiences, and showing sympathy. Experiences stimulate the development of the intellect. Because they are present in children with any deviations in mental development, emotional urges are more effective than intellectual urges. Students must understand that training the material that is provided to them assimilate learn his use V independent practical activities, which is impossible without the child's positive emotional attitude toward learning.

For the successful work of a team of specialists in an educational institution, it is necessary to observe the following conditions: continuity, consistency in action, systematic, planned, purposeful, and phased mutual corrective measures.

If the task of the teacher is to prepare and submit the material in the most accessible form, and the task of the psychologist is to unite the efforts of parents, teachers, and teachers to solve the problem that arises in the child,

Parents need to understand the two-way responsibility. Here, you can't just "hand over" the child to school and wait for the results. Parents should cooperate with the teacher and other specialists to jointly solve the problems of the child's development.

Every child has unique features, interests, abilities, and educational needs. AND ABOUT - This gradual, detailed, and very gentle process of turning on a child to general educational Wednesday takes into account individual characteristics and relies on the child's strengths.

Inclusive education gives:

Children with disabilities: freedom of personal development;

Parents: the opportunity to use their parental potential in raising a child with a developmental disorder;

School: an opportunity to expand individual educational services in order to prepare a graduate for an independent life and to educate a citizen;

Society: the possibility of improving social relations in the spirit of humanism and tolerance;

To the state: the possibility of implementing constitutional guarantees and observing international provisions

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